

GA-NIFS: JWST/NIRSpec IFS view of the $z \sim 3.5$ galaxy GS5001 and its close environment at the core of a large-scale overdensity

Appendix

Isabella Lamperti^{1,2,3,*}, Santiago Arribas¹, Michele Perna¹, Bruno Rodríguez Del Pino¹, Chiara Circosta^{4,5}, Pablo G. Pérez-González¹, Andrew J. Bunker⁶, Stefano Carniani⁷, Stéphane Charlot⁸, Francesco D'Eugenio^{9,10}, Roberto Maiolino^{9,10,5}, Hannah Übler^{9,10}, Chris J. Willott¹¹, Elena Bertola³, Torsten Böker¹², Giovanni Cresci³, Mirko Curti¹³, Gareth C. Jones⁶, Nimisha Kumari¹⁴, Eleonora Parlanti⁷, Jan Scholtz^{9,10}, and Giacomo Venturi⁷

¹ Centro de Astrobiología (CAB), CSIC-INTA, Ctra. de Ajalvir Km. 4, 28850 Torrejón de Ardoz, Madrid, Spain

² Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia, Università di Firenze, Via G. Sansone 1, 50019, Sesto F.no (Firenze), Italy

³ INAF - Osservatorio Astrofisico di Arcetri, largo E. Fermi 5, 50127 Firenze, Italy

⁴ European Space Agency (ESA), European Space Astronomy Centre (ESAC), Camino Bajo del Castillo s/n, 28692 Villanueva de la Cañada, Madrid, Spain

⁵ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University College London, Gower Street, London WC1E 6BT, UK

⁶ University of Oxford, Department of Physics, Denys Wilkinson Building, Keble Road, Oxford OX13RH, United Kingdom

⁷ Scuola Normale Superiore, Piazza dei Cavalieri 7, I-56126 Pisa, Italy

⁸ Sorbonne Université, CNRS, UMR 7095, Institut d'Astrophysique de Paris, 98 bis bd Arago, 75014 Paris, France

⁹ Kavli Institute for Cosmology, University of Cambridge, Madingley Road, Cambridge, CB3 0HA, UK

¹⁰ Cavendish Laboratory - Astrophysics Group, University of Cambridge, 19 JJ Thomson Avenue, Cambridge, CB3 0HE, UK

¹¹ NRC Herzberg, 5071 West Saanich Rd, Victoria, BC V9E 2E7, Canada

¹² European Space Agency, c/o STScI, 3700 San Martin Drive, Baltimore, MD 21218, USA

¹³ European Southern Observatory, Karl-Schwarzschild-Strasse 2, 85748 Garching, Germany

¹⁴ AURA for the European Space Agency, Space Telescope Science Institute, Baltimore, MD, USA

September 18, 2024

ABSTRACT

We present JWST Near-Infrared Spectrograph (NIRSpec) observations in Integral Field Spectroscopic (IFS) mode of the galaxy GS5001 at redshift $z=3.47$, the central member of a candidate protocluster in the GOODS-S field. The data cover a field of view (FoV) of $4'' \times 4''$ ($\sim 30 \times 30$ kpc²) and were obtained as part of the Galaxy Assembly with NIRSpec IFS (GA-NIFS) GTO program. The observations include both high ($R \sim 2700$) and low ($R \sim 100$) spectral resolution data, spanning the rest-frame wavelength ranges 3700–6780 Å and 1300–11850 Å, respectively. These observations enable the detection and mapping of the main optical emission lines from [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3726, 29$ to [S III] $\lambda 9531$. We analyse the spatially resolved ionised gas kinematics and interstellar medium properties, including obscuration, gas metallicity, excitation, ionisation parameter, and electron density. In addition to the main galaxy (GS5001), the NIRSpec FoV covers a close companion in the south, with three sub-structures with velocities blue-shifted by ~ -150 km s⁻¹ with respect to GS5001, and another source in the north redshifted by ~ 200 km s⁻¹. Optical line ratio diagnostics indicate star formation ionisation and electron densities ~ 500 cm⁻³ across all sources in the FoV. The gas-phase metallicity in the main galaxy is $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.45 \pm 0.04$, and slightly lower in the companions ($12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.34 - 8.42$), consistent with the mass-metallicity relation at $z \sim 3$. We find peculiar line ratios (high $\log[\text{N II}]/\text{H}\alpha = [-0.45, -0.3]$, low $\log[\text{O III}]/\text{H}\beta = [0.06, 0.10]$) in the northern part of GS5001. These could be attributed to either higher metallicity, or to shocks resulting from the interaction of the main galaxy with the northern source. We identify a spatially resolved outflow in the main galaxy, traced by a broad symmetric component in H α and [O III], with an extension of about 3 kpc. We find maximum outflow velocities of ~ 400 km s⁻¹, an outflow mass of $(1.7 \pm 0.4) \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$, a mass outflow rate of $23 \pm 5 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and a mass loading factor of 0.23. These properties are compatible with star formation being the driver of the outflow. Our analysis of these JWST NIRSpec IFS data therefore provides valuable, unprecedented insights into the interplay between star formation, galactic outflows and interactions in the core of a $z \sim 3.5$ candidate protocluster.

* E-mail: isabella.lamperti@unifi.it

Appendix A: Tables of the emission line fluxes

In Tables A.1 and A.2 we report the emission line fluxes measured from the spectra integrated over the different regions shown in Fig. 1, from the R2700 and R100 data cubes, respectively.

Appendix B: Example of spectral fit of one spaxel

Figure B.1 shows the spectrum extracted from one spaxel close to the centre of the main galaxy ($x, y = 44, 46$), together with the best-fit model obtained with the python routine ‘`scipy.optimize.curve_fit`’.

Appendix C: H α maps from the one-component Gaussian fit

In this section, we show the maps of the H α flux, velocity (v_{50}) and velocity dispersion, obtained from the fit with one Gaussian component (Figure C.1). These maps are qualitatively similar to the maps obtained with a variable number of components (one or two) shown in Fig. 5 of the paper.

Appendix D: Channel maps to highlight the position of clump ‘c’

In this section we show channel maps that we use to identify a clump (‘c’) at the south-west of the main galaxy. Figure D.1 shows continuum-subtracted channel maps of H α . The channels have a width of 40 km s $^{-1}$ and span the range from -80 to 240 km s $^{-1}$ with respect to the systemic redshift of the main galaxy ($z = 3.4705$). The emission at the position of the clump is visible in the channels from -40 to 160 km s $^{-1}$. In particular, the morphology in the channel 120-160 km s $^{-1}$ shows that at the clump position there is a clear peak, separated from the emission of the main galaxy.

Appendix E: Two component fit: kinematic maps of the broad component of H α

Figure E.1 shows the maps of the broad emission of H α , including all Gaussian components with $\sigma > 140$ km s $^{-1}$. The three panels show the flux, central velocity (v_{50}) and the line width (W80).

Appendix F: Fit of [S II] and [O II] for deriving the electron densities

In this section, we show the fit of [S II] and [O II] for the four regions in which we could estimate the electron density: south, north, s2, s3, n1, and n2.

We also show the fit of [S II] and [O II] lines of the main target using two components (narrow+broad). The electron density derived from the narrow component is similar to the value inferred from the one-component fit but with larger uncertainties ($n_e = 540_{-280}^{+270}$ cm $^{-3}$). The electron density of the broad component is unconstrained ($n_e = 340_{-280}^{+1400}$ cm $^{-3}$).

Appendix G: Integrated spectra

In this section we show the integrated spectra of the regions defined in Fig. 1, together with the best-fit model. In particular,

we show the spectra of the regions ‘south’ and ‘north’, the sub-structures s1, s2, s3, n1, n2, n3, and the clump ‘c’.

References

Cardelli, J. A., Clayton, G. C., & Mathis, J. S. 1989, *Astrophysical Journal*, 345, 245

Table A.1: Emission line fluxes of the different components (and sub-components) of the system, in units of $[\times 10^{-18} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}]$.

region	[O II] λ 3726	[O II] λ 3729	H γ	H β	[O III] λ 5007	[O I] λ 6300	H α	[N II] λ 6584	[S II] λ 6716	[S II] λ 6731
main	180.7 ± 1.9	127.3 ± 0.8	45.2 ± 0.4	106.8 ± 0.4	227.6 ± 0.4	7.6 ± 0.5	305.3 ± 0.8	78.6 ± 0.5	28.1 ± 0.7	20.9 ± 0.3
main n	77.9 ± 1.7	60.9 ± 0.9	28.4 ± 0.4	59.6 ± 0.6	125.8 ± 0.6	5.1 ± 0.4	170.3 ± 1.2	43.1 ± 0.7	14.6 ± 0.6	11.0 ± 0.4
main b	316.1 ± 4.0	134.0 ± 1.4	11.2 ± 0.6	89.7 ± 1.1	197.5 ± 1.8	3.1 ± 0.5	256.4 ± 4.0	63.8 ± 1.7	26.7 ± 1.1	21.1 ± 0.8
south	81.9 ± 1.6	60.1 ± 0.7	21.3 ± 0.3	45.0 ± 0.3	125.0 ± 0.4	4.5 ± 0.4	128.6 ± 0.6	18.8 ± 0.4	13.2 ± 0.7	10.7 ± 0.3
north	189.8 ± 1.0	210.9 ± 0.5	42.1 ± 0.3	63.2 ± 0.2	202.5 ± 0.3	2.5 ± 0.3	180.7 ± 0.4	29.2 ± 0.3	20.9 ± 0.4	15.7 ± 0.2
s1	8.7 ± 1.0	5.7 ± 0.4	2.1 ± 0.2	7.0 ± 0.2	20.4 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.2	20.0 ± 0.4	2.1 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.2
s2	23.4 ± 0.5	19.6 ± 0.2	5.0 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	31.2 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.1	32.9 ± 0.2	6.0 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.1
s3	30.8 ± 0.4	24.2 ± 0.2	9.3 ± 0.1	18.0 ± 0.1	54.6 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1	51.5 ± 0.2	6.9 ± 0.1	4.9 ± 0.1	3.5 ± 0.1
n1	12.0 ± 0.2	10.2 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1	17.6 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	20.5 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1
n2	24.5 ± 0.2	21.4 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.1	7.5 ± 0.1	27.2 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	21.5 ± 0.1	3.8 ± 0.1	2.1 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1
n3	99.2 ± 0.4	79.1 ± 0.2	31.3 ± 0.1	16.2 ± 0.1	78.8 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.1	46.2 ± 0.1	4.3 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.1
c	6.2 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	3.5 ± 0.1	8.2 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	10.0 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.1

Notes. Fluxes of the different components identified in Fig. 1. For the main galaxy, we report the fluxes obtained with one Gaussian component model (main) and the fluxes obtained with a two-component model (narrow (main n) and broad (main b) components). The label ‘main n’ and ‘main b’ refer to the narrow and broad component of the two-component model, respectively. For the other regions, the fluxes have been obtained with the one-component model fit. Fluxes have been corrected for obscuration using a Cardelli et al. (1989) attenuation law as described in Sec. 5.2.1.

Fig. B.1: Example of fit of the average spectrum of nine adjacent spaxels close to the centre of the ‘main’ galaxy, used for the spatially-resolved fit. Data are shown in black, the total best fit in blue, the narrow and broad components are shown in lightblue and red, respectively, shifted vertically for visual purposes. The vertical lines mark the wavelength positions of the emission lines at the systemic redshift of the source ($z = 3.4705$). The fitting residuals are shown in the bottom panel.

Fig. C.1: Maps of the observed $H\alpha$ emission obtained from the spatially resolved emission line fit with one Gaussian component. From left to right: integrated observed flux (not corrected for obscuration), 50th percentile velocity (v_{50}), line width W80 (difference between 10th and 90th percentile velocity). Contours in the flux map show the [20,40, 60, 80, 90] percentiles, contours in the v_{50} map start at -150 km s^{-1} and increase every 50 km s^{-1} , contours in the W80 map are at [200, 300, 400] km s^{-1} .

Fig. D.1: Channel maps of the $H\alpha$ emission to illustrate the position of the clump ‘c’, on the south-west of the central target. The channels have a width of 40 km s^{-1} and the velocities are given with respect to the systemic velocity. The clump ‘c’ is indicated with a blue circle and is visible in the velocity channels [0–200] km s^{-1} .

Fig. E.1: Maps of the broad emission of $H\alpha$, including all Gaussian components with $\sigma > 140 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. For the spaxels fitted with a two-Gaussian model, the broader component is shown. For the spaxels fitted with a one-component model, the component is shown only if $\sigma > 140 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. From left to right: observed flux (not corrected for attenuation), centroid velocity, and velocity dispersion (W80). Only spaxels with $S/N > 3$ are shown.

Fig. F.1: Simultaneous spectral fit of the $[\text{O II}]\lambda\lambda 3726, 29$ and $[\text{S II}]\lambda\lambda 6716, 31$ doublets to derive the electron density from the integrated spectrum of the targets south and north (upper row), s2 and s3 (middle row), n1 and n2 (lower row). The blue curve shows the total best-fit model, the light-blue curves show the best-fit Gaussians for the individual emission lines and the gray curves show the uncertainties of the MCMC fit. The bottom panels show the residuals, the dashed line shows the one-sigma error level.

Table A.2: Fluxes of the different components of the system derived from the R100 data cube, in units of $[\times 10^{-18} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}]$.

region	[S II] $\lambda 6716 + \lambda 6731$	[S III] $\lambda 9069$	[S III] $\lambda 9531$
main	55.3 ± 6.8	17.2 ± 3.3	43.1 ± 4.1
south	27.9 ± 3.6	6.8 ± 1.8	19.9 ± 2.3
north	23.0 ± 3.1	8.5 ± 1.2	21.0 ± 1.4
s1	4.0 ± 0.8	2.0 ± 0.6	3.8 ± 0.8
s2	8.2 ± 1.0	1.5 ± 0.4	4.7 ± 0.6
s3	6.5 ± 1.4	2.4 ± 0.7	7.6 ± 0.8
n1	3.0 ± 0.6	1.1 ± 0.3	2.7 ± 0.3
n2	3.8 ± 0.6	1.1 ± 0.3	2.6 ± 0.3
n3	6.7 ± 0.9	1.1 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.3
c	2.6 ± 0.4	0.6 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.3

Notes. Fluxes of the different components identified in Fig. 1. Fluxes have been corrected for obscuration using a [Cardelli et al. \(1989\)](#) attenuation law as described in Sec. 5.2.1. We report the total flux of the [S II] $\lambda 6716 +$ [S II] $\lambda 6731$ doublet, since the two lines are not resolved in the R100 data.

Fig. F.2: Simultaneous spectral fit of the [O II] $\lambda\lambda 3726, 29$ and [S II] $\lambda\lambda 6716, 31$ doublets to derive the electron density from the integrated spectrum of the main target using two components (broad and narrow). The blue curve shows the total best-fit model, the light-blue and red curves show the best-fit narrow and broad Gaussian components, respectively, for the individual emission lines. The grey curves the uncertainties of the MCMC fit. The bottom panels show the residuals.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source ‘south’. The total best fit is shown in blue. The individual narrow components are shown in lightblue, shifted vertically for visual purposes. The vertical lines mark the wavelength positions of the emission lines at the systemic redshift of the main source ($z = 3.4705$). The fitting residuals are shown in the bottom panel.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source ‘north’.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 's1'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 's2'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 's3'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 'n1'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 'n2'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 'n3'.

Fig. G.1: Integrated spectrum of source 'c'.